

EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON PREGNANCY

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Abstract. The group at highest risk for severe COVID-19 includes pregnant women with somatic diseases: chronic lung diseases, including moderate to severe bronchial asthma, cardiovascular disease, arterial hypertension, diabetes, cancer, obesity (BMI>30 kg/m²); chronic kidney disease, liver disease

Keywords: COVID-19, pregnancy, risk factors

Infectious diseases during pregnancy are potentially dangerous to both the health of the mother and the health of the unborn child. On 11 March 2020, COVID-19 was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organisation. This problem has not lost its relevance until today. Although we are in the third wave of the pandemic, the disease remains poorly understood and data on the impact of the virus on the foetus and the health of the unborn child are contradictory. But it is clear that pregnant women are more likely to have a more severe course of respiratory viral infections and a sudden onset of critical illness in the presence of stable disease due to physiological changes in the immune and cardiopulmonary systems. The group at highest risk of severe COVID-19 is pregnant women with concomitant lung disease, cardiovascular disease, arterial hypertension; diabetes mellitus; obesity; chronic kidney disease, liver disease, and antiphospholipid syndrome (APS).

When managing pregnant women in pandemic conditions, examinations should be carried out in a timely manner according to the gestational age;

- remote counselling appointments are acceptable;
- Effective communication with pregnant women in a high-stress and uncertain environment should be maintained;
- pregnant women should be in touch with their doctors to discuss their concerns about the impending delivery;
- it is recommended to keep a social distance and wear a mask and gloves when on public transport or in other crowded places (shop, train station, airport) and when visiting antenatal clinics and hospitals.

Conclusions: Around the world, many women live in close proximity to a lot of other people, which makes physical distancing much more difficult. In such places, "I would really ask the whole society to take care of pregnant women", Cade urges. She recommends that people distance themselves as much as

possible from pregnant women. There should also be separate washrooms for them.

"And don't forget the importance of hand washing. We don't talk about it all the time for nothing. COVID-19 and soap don't like each other. It's a simple measure that can do a lot of good," she says. - I do hope that in any situation that exists, the community and health workers contribute to a system and environment that is safe and secure for pregnant women, because, after all, they are giving birth to our future. That should be appreciated!"

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